

UNIR-CoARA Action Plan 2026- 2030

Prepared by the UNIR-CoARA Working Group

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Introduction

The International University of La Rioja (UNIR) is the largest private online university in the Spanish-speaking world, which places it in a central position with regard to its role as a bridge between Europe and Latin America. Research holds a priority position in the institution's policy, being one of the pillars of its Strategic Plan, and it is fostered as a valuable contribution to society. UNIR is the Spanish private university with the largest number of teaching and research staff (PDI) on its payroll, characterised by a predominantly young profile and links to a wide diversity of fields. This undoubtedly shapes the institution's role as an evaluator of its internal processes, thereby assuming a commitment to its teaching and research staff at every level, from the institutional to the individual. In this respect, it aspires to recognise and value the quality, diversity and impact of research, adapting its evaluation processes so as to reflect the plurality of scientific contributions. In this context, it seeks to promote an evaluation practice based on fairer and more transparent criteria, aligned with the ethical principles that should govern scientific activity. In this regard, the *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity* (ALLEA, 2023) constitutes a framework that serves as a prior ethical foundation, recognising research as a collective endeavour that demands shared standards of rigour and responsibility. On this basis, the need is shared to take part in global initiatives such as the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment* (CoARA), and its proposal.

Research assessment is undergoing a significant transformation that responds to the demands of the international academic community. Initiatives such as the *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment* (DORA, 2012), the *Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics* (2015), or, more recently, the establishment of the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment* (CoARA, 2022), raise the need to reform evaluation systems in order to make them fairer, more inclusive and aligned with the principles of open science. At the national level, the *Ley Orgánica 2/2023, de 22 de marzo, del Sistema Universitario* [Organic Law 2/2023, of 22 March, on the University System] (LOSU) introduces key reforms in the accreditation of university teaching staff, subsequently developed in *Real Decreto 678/2023, de 18 de julio, por el que se regula la acreditación estatal para el acceso a los cuerpos docentes universitarios y el régimen de los concursos de acceso a plazas de dichos cuerpos* [Royal Decree 678/2023, of 18 July, regulating state accreditation for access to the university teaching bodies and the system governing competitive examinations for posts within those bodies], which also

includes amendments that promote the principles of open science and the design of more transparent evaluation processes. Likewise, the [National Open Science Strategy 2023-2027](#) (ENCA), approved by the Government of Spain in June 2023, sets out as one of its strategic objectives the creation of new evaluation mechanisms that foster open science practices, such as open access publishing and the reuse of research data. ENCA also proposes a system of incentives and recognition for researchers and institutions that adopt these practices. Continuing within the national framework, it is worth highlighting the accession of the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA) to CoARA, reflecting its commitment to reforming research assessment models and to fostering a new evaluation culture that recognises the diversity of research activity. Finally, at the European level, the [Council Recommendation on enhancing research security](#) completes the regulatory framework, urging European institutions to ensure a model of research that is protected against external interference.

In this context, UNIR is committed to aligning its evaluation processes with these regulations and strategies, reinforcing its role as an innovative institution committed to research excellence. The [UNIR-CoARA Action Plan](#) presented here reflects UNIR's commitment to the continuous improvement of its evaluation systems, fostering a research culture that recognises the diversity, quality and impact of research at all its levels.

UNIR in the context of CoARA

With UNIR's accession to CoARA in April 2023, an institutional commitment was established to reform its research assessment systems, in line with the principles and commitments set out in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#). This Agreement, together with CoARA's ten core commitments and the recommendations of the document [Supporting CoARA signatories in the preparation of action plans](#), has served as a reference for the preparation of the [UNIR-CoARA Action Plan 2026-2030](#). This plan is aligned with the [UNIR Strategic Research Plan](#), a key document for defining the institution's direction and approach to research.

The plan has been prepared by the UNIR-CoARA Working Group and is designed to be developed within the framework of a participatory process open to the whole UNIR community, involving researchers from different disciplines and at different career

stages. This inclusive approach will make it possible to incorporate a broad and representative perspective into the successive updates that will take place, thereby ensuring that the needs and expectations of UNIR's research community are reflected in the design and implementation of the new evaluation policies. In addition to its young profile and the diversity of its fields of knowledge, UNIR has a notable presence of teaching and research staff with mainly professional profiles, owing to the specific needs of various training programmes. All of this means that any change or modification relating to teaching and research staff must be carried out taking into account UNIR's specific characteristics, and ensuring evaluative coherence between its internal principles and the criteria of the evaluation agencies. In this respect, the implementation of the plan's actions will be carried out in a manner compatible with the evaluation requirements established at any given time by the applicable national and regional regulations, as well as by the competent evaluation agencies. With this vision, and on a pragmatic basis, UNIR aims to provide its teaching and research staff with certainty regarding the evaluation processes to which they are subject, while aligning its internal processes with the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) and the commitments of CoARA.

Finally, it is important to note that the information contained in the plan is not definitive, since it is subject to ongoing evaluation and review, which leaves open the possibility of making any adjustments deemed necessary, which would be duly communicated. Likewise, in accordance with the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#), a comprehensive review of the plan will be carried out at the institutional level at the end of the fifth year.

Evaluation processes at UNIR

Following UNIR's accession to CoARA, and in anticipation of what is developed in this plan, a process began to take shape for reviewing the internal calls for the evaluation of teaching and research staff, aimed at progressively aligning them with the principles of the Agreement. Thus, since the 2023-2024 academic year, calls such as the Young Researchers Award or the Banco Santander Postdoctoral Fellowships have incorporated among their requirements the preparation of narrative CVs and project reports, which were subsequently evaluated by committees specialised in the fields of knowledge represented in each process. In this way, scientific quality is no longer

expressed and measured solely through quantitative indicators, and room is made for the construction of a qualitative account of the research trajectory, in keeping with the responsible use of metrics promoted by both DORA and CoARA's own Agreement. These changes represent the first steps towards an evaluation that recognises the diversity of contributions and trajectories of UNIR's teaching and research staff. The modifications are also framed within UNIR's priority research lines, which ensures coherence between the evaluation reform and the institution's strategic direction.

UNIR-CoARA Action Plan 2026-2030

The following plan sets out the lines of action to be pursued and links them to concrete actions in keeping with the 10 commitments of CoARA, which are recalled below. In this way, this representation of the actions to be undertaken serves as a roadmap for the progressive adaptation of the processes for evaluating research activity. All of this is designed in accordance with UNIR's own institutional needs, while maintaining a realistic view of the process as a whole.

The 10 commitments of CoARA

1. **Recognise** the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. **Base** research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. **Abandon** inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. **Avoid** the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.
5. **Commit** resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.
6. **Review** and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.
7. **Raise awareness** of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.

8. **Exchange** practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. **Communicate** progress made in adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. **Evaluate** practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

Line of action	Actions	CoARA commitment	Implementation	Responsible party	Milestone
1. Formation of the CoARA-UNIR Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assemble a panel with different profiles. - Establish the working procedures. 	Commitment 5	2025-2026 academic year	Vice-Rectorate for Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group's founding minutes
2. Design of the CoARA-UNIR Action Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allocate responsibilities and set out the objectives, establishing deadlines and accountabilities. - Schedule the working and monitoring meetings. - Agree and plan participation in the CoARA forums. 	Commitment 5	2025-2026 academic year	CoARA-UNIR Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Action plan drafted - Work schedule established
3. Approval of the plan by UNIR's Vice-Rectorate for Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seek institutional endorsement and validity. - Provide the plan with the necessary resources. - Agree on the frequency of monitoring the plan's development. 	Commitment 5	2025-2026 academic year	Vice-Rectorate for Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formal agreement of the vice-rectorate
4. Publication of the action plan and dissemination within the UNIR community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deposit the plan in the Zenodo and ReUNIR repositories. - Produce materials to disseminate the plan internally. - Establish communication channels between the working group and the UNIR community. 	Commitments 7, 8, 9	2026-2027 academic year	CoARA-UNIR Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan deposited - Training activities delivered

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise training sessions with teaching and research staff (PDI) and management and administrative staff (PGA). - Share the plan in the various CoARA forums. - Evaluate the plan's dissemination actions. 				
5. Review of the evaluation processes and proposal of updates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review the calls that need updating in line with the Agreement and the CoARA Principles. - Identify elements not aligned with CoARA in each call under review. - Propose updates for each call. - Evaluate the review processes carried out. 	Commitments 1, 2, 3, 4, 6	2026-2027 academic year	CoARA-UNIR Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diagnosis of actions not aligned with CoARA
6. Approval of the updates to the calls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publish the updated regulations for each call subject to the review process. - Design guidance documents for applicants and evaluators. 	Commitment 10	2026-2027 academic year	Vice-Rectorate for Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calls approved - Guidance documents produced
7. Overall evaluation and final report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare the final report on the process. - Share the report with CoARA and disseminate it within the UNIR community. - Foster collaboration and knowledge-exchange processes with other institutions with a view to the ongoing updating of the evaluation processes. 	Commitments 7, 8, 9	2026-2027 academic year	CoARA-UNIR Working Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final report

Table 1: Lines of action of UNIR's CoARA Action Plan

Conclusions

The *UNIR-CoARA Action Plan* represents the commitment of the International University of La Rioja to the continuous improvement of its research assessment processes. In keeping with international and national trends, the plan sets out the steps needed to transform the evaluation processes, seeking to make them fairer and more inclusive. This updating approach requires full correspondence between the institution's objectives and the principles of CoARA, as already set out in the *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment*. This alignment will be the basis from which to undertake the transformation process, through a dynamic plan conceived as a flexible framework subject to reviews and updates. Thus, periodic review will make it possible to make the appropriate adjustments to ensure the effectiveness of the approaches, and this flexibility will facilitate the accommodation of the Agreement and the CoARA Principles within UNIR's research assessment processes. Furthermore, the plan will be grounded in transparency and communication with the university community, which will take an active part in different stages of the process, as well as with the various CoARA forums at the international and national levels.

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